

Statistical Study of Sustainable Development Goals Indicators in Uzbekistan

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Abstract: The Sustainable Development Goals cover a broad range of social and economic issues, including poverty eradication, education, gender equality, clean water and sanitation, energy, economic growth, and sustainable cities. The environmental goals address climate change, biodiversity conservation, and sustainable consumption and production. The Sustainable Development Goals require cooperation not only between states, but also between the public, private sector, and non-governmental organizations. Achieving these goals requires the international community to unite, support each other, and embrace innovation as a driving force.

Keywords: Sustainable Development Goals statistics, economic and social processes, ecological balance, development strategy, poverty level.

INTRODUCTION

The Sustainable Development Goals are a set of important values, formed as a result of global thinking and research, through their implementation, it is possible to ensure human well-being, social stability and ecological balance. The 17 Sustainable Development Goals adopted by the UN serve as a common roadmap for all countries, that is, 193 countries, until 2030. This plan is a continuation of the Millennium Development Goals developed in 2000. This system established 8 Millennium Development Goals (MDGs), which are the first comprehensive global management system for achieving sustainable development. Thus, it is possible to trace the process of transition from the Millennium Development Goals (MDGs, 2000-2015) to the Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs, 2015-2030). The Sustainable Development Goals are significant because they aim to ensure a balance between the "three pillars" of sustainable development - economic, social, and environmental - which are closely interrelated, complementary, and mutually reinforcing.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

In order to organize systematic work on the implementation of the UN "2030 Agenda for Sustainable Development", the Cabinet of Ministers of the Republic of Uzbekistan adopted Resolutions No. 841 "On measures to implement national goals and objectives in the field of sustainable development until 2030" dated October 20, 2018 and "On additional measures to accelerate the implementation of national goals and objectives in the field of sustainable development until 2030" dated February 21, 2022.

As a result of serious interest and efforts to adapt the "Sustainable Development Goals" to the needs of the country, the results of the Action Strategy of Uzbekistan for 2017-2021 and the currently implemented "Development Strategy of New Uzbekistan for 2022-2026" can be cited.

The main principle of the Development Strategy of New Uzbekistan, approved by the Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan, "On the Path of Human Dignity and Honor,"

envisages further increasing the well-being of the people, transforming the economy, accelerating the development of entrepreneurship, ensuring human rights and interests, and forming an active civil society. At the same time, it sets itself the goal of joining the upper group of middle-income countries by ensuring an increase in per capita income to 4,000 US dollars by 2030.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Uzbekistan is implementing a national model of mahalla, which differs from other foreign countries in that it addresses issues of improving the well-being of the population, developing entrepreneurship, ensuring employment and reducing poverty, and addressing targeted social protection issues directly in the places of residence of the population (mahallas). Based on this principle, a number of institutional reforms are being implemented, the governance system is being reformed, and the development of democracy is being ensured through the broad participation of the population and civil society in all areas of economic and social policy.

The government's resolution of February 21, 2022 "On additional measures to accelerate the implementation of national goals and objectives in the field of sustainable development for the period up to 2030" expanded the tasks to achieve the 16 goals to 126, and approved 190 national SDG indicators.

Uzbekistan has risen 8 places in the international ranking of Sustainable Development Goals. In the SDG index (SDG index) published in 2023 by the Sustainable Development Solutions Network (SDSN) and international experts, Uzbekistan ranked 69th out of 166 countries with an index of 71.1. This result is an increase of 8 places compared to 2022. In 2022, Uzbekistan was ranked 77th with an index of 69.9. According to the 2023 SDG index report, Uzbekistan recorded positive growth in the following 10 Sustainable Development Goals¹:

- reducing poverty in the country;
- ensuring health and well-being;
- providing quality education;
- achieving gender equality;
- clean water and sanitation;
- industrialization, innovation and infrastructure;
- sustainable urban and human settlement development;
- combating climate change;
- peace, justice and good governance;
- partnership for sustainable development.

Table 1. Results achieved in Uzbekistan on Sustainable Development Goals indicators²

Indicators	National indicators	2019	2020	2021	2022	2023
8.1.1	Annual growth rate of real GDP per capita.	4,0	0,1	5,3	3,5	4,1
8.2.1	The annual growth rate of real GDP per person employed.	3,9	4,3	5,0	4,4	3,9
8.5.2	Unemployment rate, %	9,0	10,5	9,6	8,9	6,8
17.6.1	Number of fixed broadband Internet subscribers, by speed	2,2	3,2	4,2	5,2	6,1
17.6.1	From 256 kbit/sec. to 2 Mbit/sec.;	0,1	0,1	0,04	0,2	0,0
17.6.1	From 2 Mbit/sec. to 10 Mbit/sec.;	1,8	2,4	1,7	1,2	0,8
17.6.1	From 10 Mbit/sec to 30 Mbit/sec.;	0,2	0,6	2,1	2,6	3,4
17.6.1	From 30 Mbit/sec. to 100 Mbit/sec.;	0,05	0,1	0,3	0,8	1,0
17.6.1	Above 100 Mbit/sec	0,01	0,01	0,06	0,3	0,9

¹ <https://stat.uz>

² <https://nsdg.stat.uz/uz/databanks>

17.8.1	Percentage of the population using the Internet	70,4	71,1	76,6	83,9	89,0
17.13.1	A single set of key macroeconomic indicators:					
17.13.1	a) GDP volume, in billion soums;	532 712,5	605 514,9	738 425,2	888 341,68	1 192 162,5
17.13.1	b) GDP growth rate, in percentage terms compared to the previous year;	6,0	2,0	7,4	5,7	6,3
17.13.1	c) GDP per capita, thousand soums;	15 863,8	17 688,5	21 149,2	24919, 7	32 740,6
17.13.1	d) According to the purchasing power parity of the Uzbek soum against the US dollar:					
17.13.1	total, in billion US dollars;	259,2	267,8	300,5	339,8	354,1
17.13.1	per capita, in US dollars.	7 718	7 823	8 608	9532,5	9 725

According to Table 1, the annual growth rate of real GDP per capita was 4 percent in 2019, 0.1 percent in 2020, 5.3 percent in 2021, 3.5 percent in 2022, and 4.1 percent in 2023. The unemployment rate was 9 percent in 2019 and 6.8 percent in 2023.

The number of fixed broadband Internet subscribers increased from 2.2 percent in 2019 to 6.1 percent in 2023. The share of the population using the Internet was 70.4 percent in 2019, 89 percent in 2023, and so on.

The World Bank's report "Uzbekistan's Poverty Reduction Path: Findings from the International Comparison Program" dated May 9, 2024, states that Uzbekistan's poverty rate was halved between 2015 and 2022, making it one of the countries with the highest results among the countries of Europe and Central Asia. (World Bank data)³.

At the same time, according to the international poverty line used for upper-middle-income countries, the poverty rate in Uzbekistan decreased from 35.9 percent in 2015 to 17.3 percent in 2022, lifting 5.1 million people out of poverty.

At the same time, the report noted that the poverty rate, calculated based on the national poverty line (minimum consumption expenditure), decreased from 17 percent in 2021 to 11 percent in 2023.

In particular, in 2021-2023, 1.2 million people in rural areas (poverty rate in 2021 - 19.8 percent; in 2023 - 12 percent) and 400 thousand people in cities (13.9 percent; 10.1 percent) were lifted out of poverty.

In turn, the economists of the Institute of Macroeconomic and Territorial Studies and the Ministry of Economy and Finance analyzed the data showing the reduction of poverty and the change in the standard of living of the population. In particular:

1. Despite the fact that the number of households increased from 6.2 million to 7.3 million in 2015-2023, while in 2015, 4 out of 10 households had a car, in 2023 this figure increased to 6 (from 2.6 million to 4 million in total).

In particular, the number of new passenger cars sold in the domestic market increased from 186 thousand in 2015 (local cars - 178.4 thousand; imports - 7.2 thousand) to almost 500 thousand (420 thousand; 80 thousand) in 2023.

2. In 2017-2023, 419 thousand citizens were allocated mortgage loans worth 67 trillion soums, and a total of 358 thousand new apartment buildings were commissioned.

For information: in 1991-2016, 105 thousand apartment buildings were built.

3. The number of air conditioners per 100 households increased from 32 in 2015 to 47 in 2023 (a 47% increase), computers increased from 47 to 66 (40%), and vacuum cleaners increased from 53 to 71 (34%).

³ <https://brmnnt.uz/uz/newid/373>

4. The number of subscribers connected to the Internet increased from 8.3 million in 2015 to 26.7 million by 2022 (3.2 times), and the coverage of the population with Internet services increased from 26 percent to 71 percent, or full coverage of the population over 15 years of age.

5. The increase in incomes of the population has stimulated demand for private schools, allowing their number to increase from 30 in 2018 to 350 by 2023.

The number of students in higher education institutions has increased from 270 thousand in the 2016/2017 academic year to 1.4 million in the 2023/2024 academic year, and higher education coverage has increased from 9% to 42%.

In addition, more than 26 thousand non-state kindergartens were established in 2018-2023, and 788 thousand children are currently enrolled in preschool education in them. As a result, the level of preschool education coverage has increased from 25.4% in 2017 to 74.4% in 2023.

6. According to the statistics agency, the number of citizens traveling abroad for tourism purposes increased from 295 thousand in 2016 to 661 thousand in 2023 (growth - 2.2 times), and the import of tourism services increased from \$ 340 million to \$ 1.3 billion.

At the same time, the number of people going on the "Hajj" and "Umrah" pilgrimage increased from 13 thousand in 2016 to 115 thousand in 2023, and 537 thousand pilgrims visited Saudi Arabia over the past 8 years.

At the same time, the average number of flights per week from Uzbekistan to Turkish cities alone was 10 in 2016, while in 2023 this figure reached 90.

In 2015-2023, the number of hotel visitors increased by 1 million, and during this period 506 hotels with an additional 24.4 thousand beds were commissioned.

7. The volume of passenger traffic in aviation increased from 2.5 million in 2015 to 10.4 million in 2023, of which the number of domestic passenger traffic increased from 602 thousand to 1.9 million.

8. In 2015–2023, the average monthly wage increased by 4 times (in 2023 - 4.6 million soums), the number of jobs in the formal sector increased from 5.3 million to 6.5 million, and in 2020–2023, more than 2.5 million people were provided with employment through self-employment.

The number of operating business entities increased from 491 thousand in 2016 to 811 thousand in 2023, or 1.7 times.

At the same time, in 2022–2023, almost 200 thousand hectares of land intended for agriculture were allocated to 675 thousand families on a long-term lease basis.

In general, the increase in population incomes has created a basis for an increase in the volume of loans, and the balance of loans allocated to individuals has increased from 14 trillion soums in 2017 to 150 trillion soums in 2023, or an 11-fold increase.

CONCLUSION

In Uzbekistan, SDG statistics will help assess the progress of SDGs, plan policies at the national and regional levels, and prepare reports for international cooperation. This will require improving the SDG monitoring system, using Artificial Intelligence and Big Data methods, and adapting Sustainable Development Programs on the ground. Modern statistical methods, as well as cooperation between the public and private sectors, are essential for implementing this research. Strengthening domestic and international cooperation is essential for Uzbekistan to achieve the Sustainable Development Goals.

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